

Synthesis of a Few Acid Hydrazides: Sulphonyl Hydrazides and Their Derivatives from 2-Phenyl-1,2,3-Triazole-4-Carboxylic Acid and 4-Nitrophenylmercapto Acetic Acid as Antibacterial

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Manuscript received 2 February 1976; revised 26 April 1976; accepted 9 June 1976

The hydrazides of 2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid; 2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid-4'-sulphonyl chloride; 4-nitrophenyl mercapto acetic acid were obtained and their N-benzylidene derivatives were prepared. 2-Phenyl-4-(2'-aryl substituted amino-1', 3', 4'-oxadiazolyl)-1,2,3-triazole and 4-aryl substituted-5-mercapto-3-(4'-nitrophenylmercapto methyl)-1,2,4-triazole were prepared from the acid hydrazides. All the hydrazides and their N-benzylidene derivatives were screened for antibacterial activity.

IN view of encouraging results obtained during the course of earlier work on the synthesis and antibacterial screening of a few acid hydrazides and sulphonyl hydrazides and their N-benzylidene derivatives^{1,2} and synthesis of 1,2,4-triazoles³, it was thought of interest to extend such work and study their antibacterial and pharmacological properties.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of acid hydrazides (II, XII), sulphonyl hydrazides (VIII) from 2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid (I) and 4-nitrophenylmercapto acetic acid (XI) and their N-benzylidene derivatives. 2-Phenyl-4-(2'-aryl substituted amino-1', 3', 4'-oxadiazolyl)-1,2,3-triazole (V) from 2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid (I) and 4-aryl substituted-5-mercapto-3-(4'-nitrophenylmercapto methyl)-1,2,4-triazole (XV) from 4-nitrophenylmercapto acetic acid (XI) were synthesised and pharmacological studies on these compounds are in progress. All the hydrazides and their N-benzylidene derivatives have been screened for their antibacterial activity.

SCHEME-A

SCHEME-B

VI, R = H
 VII, R = SO₂Cl
 VIII, R = SO₂NHNH₂
 IX, R = SO₂NHN = CH-Ar

SCHEME-C

X, R = SH
 XI, R = SCH₂COOH
 XII, R = SCH₂CONHNH₂
 XIII, R = SCH₂CONHN = CHAr
 XIV, R = SCH₂CONHNH-CNH-Ar

Experimental

2-Phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid⁵ and 4-nitrothiophenol⁶ were obtained by the method reported in the literature. The melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

Condensation of II with aryl aldehydes (III) (Table 1)

2-Phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid (I) was esterified and the ester was then treated with 95% hydrazine hydrate^{1,2} to furnish 2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid hydrazide (II), m.p. 172°, yield 78% (Found : C, 53.17; H, 4.40 N, 3.46%, C₉H₉N₅O requires : C, 53.20; H, 4.3; N, 3.48%). Equimolar amounts of hydrazide (II) and appropriate aromatic aldehyde were refluxed with ethanol for about 2 hr. The product separated on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

2-Phenyl-4-(2'-aryl substituted amino-1',3',4'-oxadiazolyl)-1,2,3-triazole (V) (Table 2)

2-Phenyl-4-(2'-arylsubstituted amino-1',3',4'-oxadiazolyl)-1,2,3-triazoles were obtained from the appropriate thiosemicarbazides³ by the procedure of Singh *et al.*⁴, with one modification in that methanol was used as the solvent.

Chlorosulphonation of VI

0.1 mole 2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid (VI) was dissolved in 50 ml chloroform and (0.6 mole) chlorosulphonic acid was added dropwise with stirring at 5°-10°. The mixture was then refluxed on a water bath at 70° for 4 hr. Chloroform was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the residual mass poured onto crushed ice. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from a large amount of petroleum ether (40°-60°), resulting in a pale yellow solid m.p. 91°-92°, yield 68% (Found : C, 37.51; H, 2.10; N, 14.49; S, 11.06; Cl, 12.23%. C₉H₈N₃O₄SCl requires : C, 37.56; H, 2.09; N, 14.60; S, 11.13; Cl, 12.37%).

2-Phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid-4'-sulphonyl hydrazide (VIII)

2-Phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid-4-sulphonyl hydrazide was obtained from (VII) by the method of Fernandes *et al.*². M.P. 180°-182°, yield 72% (Found : C, 38.13; H, 3.14; N, 24.68; S, 11.24%, C₉H₈N₅O₄S requires : C, 38.16; H, 3.18; N, 24.74; S, 11.31%).

N-Benzylidene-2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylic acid-4'-sulphonyl hydrazide (IX) were prepared by condensation with equimolar amounts of appropriate aryl aldehydes according to the method given above. The results are depicted in Table 3.

TABLE 1—N-BENZYLIDENE-2-PHENYL-1,2,3-TRIAZOLE-4-CARBOXYLIC ACID HYDRAZIDE(III)

S. No.	R =	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis					
					Found %			Calcd. %		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	C ₆ H ₆	196	78	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₅ O	65.89	4.41	24.01	65.98	4.47	24.05
2.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (<i>p</i> -)	227	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₅ O ₂	57.09	3.52	24.94	57.15	3.57	25.00
3.	C ₆ H ₄ OH(<i>o</i> -)	171	81	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂	62.50	4.21	22.71	62.54	4.24	22.80
4.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (<i>p</i> -)	150	79	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂	63.46	4.60	21.74	63.54	4.67	21.80
5.	C ₄ H ₄ O	195	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂	54.75	3.91	24.88	59.78	3.95	24.91

TABLE 2—2-PHENYL-4-(2'-ARYLSUBSTITUTED AMINO-1',3',4'- OXADIAZOLYL)-1,2,3-TRIAZOLE (V)

S. No.	R =	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis					
					Found %			Calcd. %		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
6.	C ₆ H ₅	224	46	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₆ O	63.10	3.91	27.62	63.16	3.95	27.64
7.	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>p</i> -)	175	51	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₆ O	64.31	4.06	26.45	64.34	4.10	26.50
8.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(<i>p</i> -)	262	48	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₆ OCl	56.65	3.21	24.79	56.72	3.25	24.82

4-Nitrophenylmercapto acetic acid (IX)

To 4-nitrothiophenol⁶ (0.1 mole) dissolved in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide was added slowly (0.1 mole) chloroacetic acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. Excess of ethanol was distilled under reduced pressure and the solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the volume concentrated. A precipitate results on cooling which was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. M.P. 155°-157°, yield 63% (Found: C, 44.98; H, 3.23; N, 6.48; S, 15.01%, C₈H₇NO₄S requires: C, 45.07; H, 3.27; N, 6.57; S, 15.03%).

4-Nitrophenyl mercapto acetic acid hydrazide (XII) was prepared by similar procedures as reported earlier and the product was recrystallised from ethanol. M.P. 140°-141°, yield 86%. (Found: C, 42.24; H, 3.94; N, 18.43; S, 14.02%, C₈H₉N₃O₃S requires: C, 42.30; H, 3.97; N, 18.50; S, 14.10%).

N-Benzylidene-4-nitrophenylmercapto acetic acid hydrazide (XIII) were prepared by condensing equimolar quantities of (XII) with appropriate aldehydes as above. The results are entered in Table 4.

4-Nitrothiophenylaceto thiosemicarbazide (XIV) (Table 5).

An equimolar quantity of XII and different aryl isothiocyanates was refluxed in ethanol for 3 hr. On cooling the solid product separated, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

4-Aryl substituted-5-mercapto-3-(4'-nitrophenylmercapto methyl)-1,2,4-triazole (XV) (Table 6).

0.01 mole of thiosemicarbazide XIV and 2N sodium hydroxide (20 ml) were refluxed for 3 hr. The solution was cooled, filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The product separating

TABLE 3—N-BENZYLIDENE-2-PHENYL-1,2,3-TRIAZOLE-4-CARBOXYLIC ACID-4'-SULPHONYL HYDRAZIDE (IX)

S. No.	R =	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis							
					C	Found% H	Found% N	S	C	Calcd.% H	Calcd.% N	S
9.	C ₆ H ₅	215	76	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S	51.82	3.46	18.88	8.61	51.89	3.51	18.92	8.65
10.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p-)	235	84	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₆ S	46.09	2.81	20.13	7.62	46.15	2.86	20.19	7.69
11.	C ₆ H ₄ OH(o-)	252	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₅ S	49.58	3.31	18.02	8.23	49.61	3.36	18.09	8.27
12.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p-)	205	77	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅ S	50.79	3.69	17.41	7.90	50.87	3.74	17.46	7.98
13.	C ₆ H ₄ O	220	74	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₅ S	46.48	3.01	19.34	8.81	46.53	3.05	19.39	8.86

TABLE 4—N-BENZYLIDENE-4-NITROPHENYLMERCAPTO ACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDE (XIII)

S. No.	R =	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis							
					C	Found% H	Found% N	S	C	Calcd.% H	Calcd.% N	S
14.	C ₆ H ₅	179	69	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	57.08	3.21	13.28	10.10	57.15	3.28	13.33	10.16
15.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p-)	220	81	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₅ S	49.95	3.29	15.51	8.81	50.00	3.33	15.56	8.89
16.	C ₆ H ₄ OH(o-)	193	76	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S	54.32	3.88	12.62	9.62	54.39	3.92	12.69	9.67
17.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p-)	173	74	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	55.09	4.30	12.11	9.20	55.15	4.35	12.17	9.27
18.	C ₆ H ₄ O	185	78	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S	51.10	3.56	13.69	10.42	51.15	3.61	13.77	10.49

TABLE 5—4-NITROTHIOPHENYLACETO THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (XIV)

S. No.	R =	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis							
					C	Found% H	Found% N	S	C	Calcd.% H	Calcd.% N	S
19.	C ₆ H ₅	163	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	54.50	4.21	16.92	19.65	54.55	4.24	16.97	19.70
20.	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p-)	187	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	51.01	4.22	14.83	16.96	51.06	4.26	14.89	17.02
21.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p-)	172	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	45.21	3.22	14.08	16.08	45.30	3.28	14.13	16.14

TABLE 6—4-ARYLSUBSTITUTED-5-MERCAPTO-3-(4'-NITROPHENYLMERCAPTO METHYL)-1,2,4-TRIAZOLE (XV)

S. No.	R =	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis							
					C	Found% H	Found% N	S	C	Calcd.% H	Calcd.% N	S
22.	C ₆ H ₅	237	51	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	52.28	3.41	16.22	18.54	52.32	3.49	16.28	18.60
23.	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p-)	250	54	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	53.54	3.88	15.58	17.81	53.60	3.91	15.64	17.87
24.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p-)	260	52	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Cl	47.50	2.86	14.72	16.84	47.55	2.91	14.79	16.90

was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. This procedure was followed to prepare other 1,2,4-triazoles.

Screening for antibacterial activity

Compounds II, VIII and XII and those listed in Tables 1, 3 and 4 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity. The test organisms employed were as follows :

Bacillus subtilis, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella flexneri*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by ditch-plate technique⁷, using concentration levels of 1 mg and 3 mg per ml.

Compound II inhibited the growth of *B. subtilis*, *Staph. aureus* and *Shi. flexneri* at the concentration level of 1 mg per ml. whilst there was complete inhibition of all the organisms employed at the concentration of 3 mg per ml. Compound VIII completely inhibited the growth of *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis*, *Staph. aureus* and *Shi. flexneri* at the concentration of 3 mg per ml. Compound XII partially inhibited the growth of *Staph. aureus* and *B. subtilis* at the concentration of 1 mg per ml whilst these organisms

were completely inhibited at the concentration of 3 mg per ml. All the other compounds listed in Tables 1, 3 and 4 were found to be completely ineffective against all the organisms employed.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Rev. Dr. L. Pereira, S.J., Principal and Head, Department of Microbiology, St. Xavier's College for providing laboratory facilities for microbiological testing.

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